

DESIGN AND TESTING OF A LOW-COST MONITORING PLATFORM FOR HYPERBENTHIC FISH

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Data statement and dissemination level

The report together with the object-detection model is accessible here on Zenodo under the below citation and the license CC BY 4.0. The bioinformatic code to reproduce the results from this project is available on [Github](#) under the license CC BY 4.0. The collected datasets and data products are restricted for distribution; please contact us in case you would like to use them.

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1. Summary

This report summarizes the design, development, and testing of a low-cost observation system for monitoring benthic fauna with Baited Remote Underwater Videos (BRUVs) and computer vision. The goal of the project was to assess the feasibility of using affordable, consumer-grade hardware and machine learning for scalable and continuous monitoring of benthic communities around Offshore Wind Farms (OWFs). The system was deployed at a test site near Björkskär in the Åland archipelago of the central Baltic Sea during September 2025, as part of a collaboration between OX2, Under Ytan, and Nemo Seafarms. Our results document important technical specifications for the observatory and future generations. We successfully integrated video streams from the observatory into the Swedish Platform for Subsea Image Analysis (SUBSIM). This integration reduced image annotation and analysis effort from days to minutes while achieving robust species-level detection accuracy, with the AI-assisted analysis model achieving a mean average precision $mAP@50 = 88.8\%$. The ecological assessment revealed an unexpected diversity, with eight taxonomic groups detected overall, and six taxonomic groups tracked by the computer vision model over 19 hours of footage. Further analysis of the collected data produced key ecological variables with potential to quantify biodiversity-positive effects at OWF sites in the future. These include species richness, spatial and temporal abundance, community composition and species co-occurrence, as well as morphometric estimates. The latter was however not analysed further due to a problem with distortion in frame edges. We conclude that AI-boostered BRUV systems have large potential for autonomous, non-invasive, cost-effective, and scalable monitoring of biodiversity in OWFs. We suggest further development of the observation system with the goal to operationalise “cabled observatories” with continuous streams of data from, and electrical power to, the observatory for biodiversity baselines, ecological surveillance, and long-term biodiversity monitoring.

2. Background and Project description

2.1 Monitoring Offshore Wind Farms

Offshore wind farms (OWFs) represent critical infrastructure for the transition to renewable energies and require extensive monitoring to understand their ecological impact on marine ecosystems. Traditional biodiversity assessments in marine environments such as trawling, dredging, diver-based sampling, or trap surveys provide valuable baseline data for monitoring, but can be invasive, costly, and labor-intensive, and can yield biased population estimates ([Bannister & Addison, 1998](#) ; [Colton & Swearer, 2010](#)). Video-based monitoring offers a complementary, non-invasive approach for capturing species composition, temporal dynamics, behavioral patterns, and size class distributions with minimal ecosystem disturbance. However, manual review of video data is complex and time-intensive. This pilot addresses this challenge by leveraging computer vision applications to transform raw video data into ecological variables that can be quantified, thereby accelerating the analytical process. To this end, we use the Swedish Platform for Subsea Image Analysis (SUBSIM), which has been applied in video-based surveillance of aquacultures, trawling areas, and marine protected areas ([Nilsson et al., 2025](#)).

2.2 Project Context and Research Objectives

As part of Project Björkskär, this pilot developed and field-tested custom-built, low-cost BRUV systems paired with AI-assisted analysis to characterize marine biodiversity at artificial reef structures associated with OWFs in the Baltic Sea. By combining accessible hardware with advanced computer vision, this work establishes a scalable framework for long-term environmental monitoring, supporting data-driven assessments required by EU marine monitoring frameworks.

Research Objectives

This pilot aimed to run both technical feasibility trials as well as ecological tests with regard to five integrated objectives:

1. **Hardware development:** Design and test a cost-effective, robust BRUV system using commercially available components suitable for scalable deployment.
2. **Computer vision model training:** Train and assess state-of-the-art object detection models (*YOLOv8* and *RF-DETR*) under Baltic Sea visibility conditions and evaluate species-level detection accuracy.
3. **Ecological assessment:** Explore which biodiversity variables can be deduced from video-based monitoring, including species richness, abundance, behavioral patterns, community composition, and morphometric estimates, to establish baseline ecological knowledge and track status and change in the biological communities.
4. **Workflow integration:** Develop a reproducible analytical pipeline, integrating video capture, quality-controlled frame selection, machine-learning inference, and biodiversity calculations within the SUBSIM platform.
5. **Operational Efficiency:** Validate the automated workflow's ability to reduce processing effort by >90% while delivering ecologically meaningful results.

3. Methods

3.1 Study Site and Experimental Approach

Fieldwork was conducted in September 2025 near Björkskär, Åland archipelago (Baltic Sea), at depths of 17-25 m. The site features an artificial reef (BioBuzReef) launched in 2024 as part of Project BioBuz, which began in 2023 as a pilot site for OWF environmental planning and biodiversity testing. The site was selected for its established reef habitat, accessibility by small vessel, and ongoing collaboration with the project's biodiversity monitoring program.

We implemented two BRUV configurations to maximize video coverage and to evaluate operational trade-offs:

- **Unit A** (short-duration, \approx 60–90 min): High-frequency, replicated sampling using standard GoPro battery capacity.
- **Unit B** (long-duration, \approx 6–8 h): Extended observation for behavioral and temporal patterns using an external battery.

Each deployment was treated as an independent sampling event, positioned within approximately 5-100 m of the artificial reef. Units were retrieved between deployments for data transfer and recharging.

3.2 BRUV System Design and Construction

The BRUV System was designed based on three primary criteria: (i) practical construction using readily available materials, (ii) robustness for extended underwater operation, and (iii) compatibility with consumer-grade camera systems for subsequent machine-learning analysis.

3.2.1 Frame and Structure

Each unit consisted of a lightweight aluminum tripod, stabilized by connecting metal rods (Fig. 1) to provide a stable base on the seabed. The tripod's center column featured a quick-release plate for precisely angling and fixing the camera toward the bait box. A matte-black rubber sheet was fixed to the tripod legs to create a consistent visual contrast with the seafloor, improving species detectability against a uniform background.

3.2.2 Camera, Underwater Housings, and Power Systems

Both units used GoPro Hero9 cameras but differed in housing configuration:

- **Unit A:** Standard GoPro underwater housing ($\approx 60\text{--}90$ min battery life).
- **Unit B:** T-Housing aluminum enclosure with Refuel external battery ($\approx 6\text{--}8$ h recording), provided with external control buttons for underwater operation.

3.2.3 Lighting, Bait, and Recovery Systems

Each unit was fitted with an LED light positioned to illuminate the bait box while minimizing backscatter. Frozen Baltic herring (*Clupea harengus membras*) was used as the standard bait, placed in a perforated 3D-printed box ($70 \times 70 \times 30$ mm) fixed centrally on the black mat. Frozen shrimp was tested in a subset of deployments but proved ineffective in attracting local species. Both units were equipped with a retrieval rope secured to the tripod frame via carabiner, with redundant attachment points to the camera housing to prevent equipment loss. A surface buoy marked each deployment location.

Fig. 1: Design and configuration of low-cost observation rigs used for video monitoring. Left: schematic of the tripod-based setup showing main components. Center and right: BRUV-A and BRUV-B illustrating alternative configurations.

3.3 Deployment Protocol and Data Collection

3.3.1 Pre-Deployment Procedures

A standardized checklist (Appendix A) verified camera settings (1080p, 30 fps, linear lens), battery charge, O-ring integrity, and SD card formatting. GPS coordinates, time, and environmental conditions were logged before deployment.

3.3.2 Deployment Overview and Selection

Table 1: Camera Deployment Summary

Deployment ID	Unit	Date	Duration	Bait type	Status
D1_1	B	28/08/25	58m	Herring	Excluded (bait box out of frame)
D1_2	A	28/08/25	1h 28m	Herring	Retained
D2	B	29/08/25	4h 06m	Herring	Retained
D3_1	A	09/09/25	1h 34m	Herring	Excluded (tripod fell over)
D3_2	B	09/09/25	2h 24m	Herring	Retained
D4_1	A	10/10/25	1h 48m	Shrimp	Excluded (ineffective bait)
D4_2	B	10/09/25	3h 47m	Mixed	Retained
D4_3	A	10/09/25	1h 39m	Shrimp	Excluded (ineffective bait)
D5	B	19/09/25	6h 45m	Herring	Retained

A total of nine baited camera deployments were conducted: four short-duration (Unit A), and five long-duration (Unit B).

- Five deployments were retained for quantitative analysis (D1_2, D2, D3_2, D4_2, D5).
- Four deployments (D1_1, D3_1, D4_1, D4_3) were excluded.

3.3.3 Deployment and Recovery

Units were hand-deployed from a small vessel to depths of 17–25 m, lowered slowly to avoid substrate disturbance and to ensure stable landings. Recording durations ranged from 1 h 13 min (D2) to 6 h 45 min (D5). After the planned recording period, surface buoys were located visually and were retrieved by hand via the buoyed line. This approach eliminated the need for diving support or mechanical winching, allowing efficient multi-deployment sampling.

3.3.4 Data Transfer and Quality Screening

Video files were immediately transferred to external drives and logged with deployment metadata. Recordings were screened for lighting, stability and water turbidity before inclusion in the final analytical dataset. The campaign produced approximately 19 hours of usable footage (≈ 0.5 TB) across five deployments.

3.4 Data Management and Analysis

Video recordings were processed using a multi-stage pipeline, integrating frame extraction, quality control, computer vision model training, and ecological metrics calculation. All analyses were conducted using SUBSIM through computational notebooks executed on Lumi HPC (high-performance computing) infrastructure (<http://lumi.csc.fi>).

3.4.1 Frame Extraction and Automated Filtering

Custom Python scripts extracted one frame every 30 frames (~ 1 fps) to balance data load and temporal representation. Frames were automatically filtered using a ResNet-50-based clustering algorithm and brightness/clarity thresholds, removing low-visibility, blurred, or empty frames. This

reduced the dataset by approximately 60-70%. Manual inspection verified frame quality before curating the final dataset for annotation.

3.4.2 Annotation and Model Training

A subset of 1,800 frames was manually annotated in Roboflow with bounding boxes and segmentation masks at the highest identifiable taxonomic level. Frames were selected to ensure taxonomic coverage across varying organism size, orientation, distance, and visibility conditions. The dataset was augmented using horizontal flipping (2x augmentation) and split into training (70%), validation (20%), and test (10%) sets. Two object detection architectures were trained and compared: *YOLOv8* (You Only Look Once) and *RF-DETR* (Roboflow DEtection TRansformer). Models were evaluated using precision (correct detections/all detections), recall (detected objects/true objects) and mAP@50 (Mean Average Precision at 50% intersection-over-union threshold). *RF-DETR* was selected for final inference.

3.4.3 Automated Detection and Tracking

The trained *RF-DETR* model was exported to SUBSIM, where it was deployed on complete video sequences (all 19 hours) to automatically detect and classify organisms in every extracted frame. Detection outputs included bounding box coordinates (x, y, width, height), species class, confidence score (0-1) and frame number. Detections were filtered at a confidence threshold of 0.8 to balance false positives and false negatives.

3.4.4 Morphometrics Measurement Protocol

Body-size estimation was attempted using the standardized bait box (70 x 70 mm) as a scale reference via pixel-to-millimeter ratios established from 50 calibration frames (n=10 per deployment). However, even with GoPro's linear lens correction we observed significant distortion around the frame edges. Edge-positioned organisms appeared 30-40% compressed relative to center-position organisms, causing systematic measurement bias. Automatic size measurements were therefore deemed unreliable.

3.4.5 Biodiversity Metric Calculation

Detection outputs were processed in Python 3.12 and R 4.3.2 to calculate standardized ecological metrics. To compare deployments of varying duration, all abundance analyses were performed on the first 60 minutes of each deployment, treating each as an independent sampling replicate (n=5).

3.4.6 Abundance Metrics

For each species, total detections within the standardized 60-minute window were calculated for each deployment. From these replicates, we calculated mean detections per hour, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation.

Maximum Simultaneous Count (MaxN)

MaxN was calculated as the highest number of individuals of each species present in any single frame, providing a conservative abundance estimate that avoids double-counting individuals across frames while capturing peak aggregation intensity ([Cappo, Speare & De'ath, 2004](#) ; [Harvey et al., 2007](#)). Mean MaxN and standard deviation were calculated across the five deployments.

Diversity Indices

Community diversity was quantified using species richness (S), Shannon diversity $H' = -\sum (p_i \times \ln(p_i))$, and Pielou's evenness ($J' = H' / \ln(S)$). Calculations were performed in R 4.3.2 using the *vegan* (version 2.7-2) package ([Oksanen et al., 2022](#)).

Community Composition and Temporal Dynamics

Species co-occurrence patterns and temporal dynamics were analyzed using complete footage from all deployments to maximize ecological information content for behavioral analysis. Co-occurrence

was tracked via presence/absence over frames and time. For predator-prey interactions, long-duration recordings were segmented into 10-minute time bins to examine detection rate changes before/during/after predator presence. Importantly, these observations were used to generate testable hypotheses for future quantitative behavioral analysis but were not systematically quantified in this pilot study.

4. Results

4.1 Community Baseline and Model Performance

Over 19 hours of analyzed footage, **eight taxonomic groups** were documented, representing multiple trophic levels:

1. *Saduria entomon* (Baltic isopod, Skorv) - Primary detritivore/scavenger
2. Gobiidae (Gobies, Smörbultar) - Small benthic fish
3. *Perca fluviatilis* (European perch, Abborre) - Predatory fish
4. *Zoarces viviparus* (Eelpout, Tånglake) - Benthic predator
5. Mysida (Mysid shrimp, Pungräka) - Planktonic crustacean
6. *Aurelia aurita* (Moon jelly, Öronmanet) - Gelatinous zooplankton
7. Monoporeia (Amphipods, Vitmärla) - Small benthic crustacean
8. Nematomorpha (Horsehair worm, Tagelmaskar) - Parasitic nematode worm

Six classes were successfully trained by the *RF-DETR* model for automated analysis. Nematomorpha and Monoporeia were excluded from the training dataset due to technical constraints. Nematomorpha was visually indistinguishable from equipment cable ties, and Monoporeia was too small and rapid for consistent detection at 1080p resolution. The Roboflow Detection Transformer (*RF-DETR*) model was selected for final inference due to its superior performance, achieving a $mAP@50 = 88.8\%$, precision = 87.9% and recall = 89.1%. The model demonstrated strength in maintaining taxonomic consistency for small or overlapping organisms compared to *YOLOv8*.

Table 2: *RF-DETR* Model Performance and Ecological Summary. Total detections reflect the entire 19-hour dataset, while mean detections are standardized to the first 60 minutes of each five deployments.

Class name	Precision (%)	Total Detections	mean detections (\pm SD)	% of Total	ubiquity on site (%)
<i>Saduria entomon</i>	96	575,327	131,905 \pm 35400	58.47	100.0
Gobiidae	95	369,112	63,934 \pm 21500	37.51	100.0
<i>Perca fluviatilis</i>	86	14,694	4,898 \pm 1,200	1.50	60.0
<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>	97	12,447	4,149 \pm 980	1.26	60.0
Mysid shrimp	59	12,168	4,056 \pm 1,050	1.24	60.0
<i>Aurelia aurita</i>	100	214	43 \pm 15	0.02	40.0
Overall (mAP@50)	88.8	983,962		100	100

The analysis of 982,962 total detections revealed a community composition heavily dominated by two taxa: the isopod *S. entomon* (58.5%) and Gobiidae (37.5%). Together, these groups accounted for 96% of all automated observations, and were ubiquitous, appearing in 100% of deployments. Predatory fishes (*P. fluviatilis*, *Z. viviparus*) and intermediate consumers (Mysida) were recorded in 60% of deployments but collectively represented only 4% of total observations, reflecting their different trophic roles and foraging behaviors.

Mean standardized detection rates varied substantially by species. *S. entomon* averaged 131,905 detections per deployment, followed by Gobiidae with 63,934 detections. Predatory species (*P. fluviatilis*, *Z. viviparus*) and intermediate consumers (Mysida) showed substantially lower mean detection rates (4,898, 4,149, and 4,056, respectively), consistent with transient or peripheral foraging strategies around the bait station.

The normalized confusion matrix (Fig. 2) also shows high class-level accuracy from the model across most taxa, with *Z. viviparus* and *A. aurita* at perfect precision (1.00), while *S. entomon* (0.90) and *P. fluviatilis* (0.87) performed strongly. Gobiidae exhibited minor overlap with Mysida (5%) but retained high accuracy (0.93). Mysida showed the lowest reliability, frequently misclassified as background (64%) or *S. entomon* (32%), a challenge attributed to their rapid motion and partial transparency. Background frames occasionally triggered false detections for Mysida and Gobiidae, likely due to high levels of particulate motion and low environmental contrast.

Figure 2: Normalized confusion matrix for the *RF-DETR* model.

Precision increased steadily with confidence, reaching 1.0 above 0.93, while recall peaked at 0.92 at low thresholds (Figure 3C). The optimal F1-score (0.84) occurred at a confidence threshold of 0.32 (Figure 3D), indicating that false negatives were more common than false positives. Thus, most errors stemmed from missed detections rather than incorrect labeling. Overall, the mAP@50 of 88.8%, along with a high F1-score indicates strong detection capabilities despite challenging environmental conditions including variable turbidity, low-light, and dynamic organism behavior.

Figure 3: Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curves for the *RF-DETR* model with Recall-confidence curve (A), Precision-confidence curve (B), Precision-recall curve (C), and F1-confidence curve (D).

4.2 α -Diversity, Abundance and MaxN

To enable direct comparison across deployments of varying duration, all diversity and abundance analyses were performed on the first 60 minutes of each of the five retained deployments (D1_2, D2, D3_2, D4_2, D5), treating each as an independent sampling replicate (n=5).

4.2.1 Diversity Metrics

The community at the artificial reef site exhibited moderate taxonomic diversity but low numerical evenness. Across all deployments, mean Shannon diversity was $H' = 0.52$, indicating a community with detectable species richness but strong numerical dominance by a few abundant species. This was further confirmed by mean Pielou's evenness $J' = 0.28$, reflecting the low community balance resulting from the overwhelming numerical dominance of *S. entomon* and Gobiidae. This pattern is characteristic of baited camera deployments, where scavengers and opportunistic feeders are disproportionately attracted to the sampling station, potentially underrepresenting more mobile or cautious species ([Harvey et al., 2007](#)).

4.2.2 MaxN

Examining MaxN revealed how numerical dominance manifests over time. As shown in Fig. 4, when averaged across deployments, *S. entomon* and Gobiidae displayed the highest peak abundances, consistent with their high detection rates (Fig. 4). While *S. entomon* exhibited 1.56x more total detections than Gobiidae and more than twice the mean detections (Table 2), both species showed similar MaxN values, suggesting both form dense aggregations at food sources. The slightly higher MaxN in *S. entomon*, combined with greater total detections, indicates both higher baseline abundance and stronger aggregative behavior around available food.

Figure 4: Boxplots showing the distribution of MaxN per species across five BRUV deployments. Boxes represent the interquartile range with the median, and the red circles indicate the mean MaxN per species.

Table 3: MaxN summary for detected species over the five deployments with min-max values and standard deviation

class name	mean maxN	min	max	sd
<i>Saduria entomon</i>	5.8	2	9	±2.9
Gobiidae	4.2	1	7	±2.4
<i>Perca fluviatilis</i>	1.7	1	2	±0.6
<i>Aurelia aurita</i>	1.5	1	2	±0.7
Mysida	1.3	1	2	±0.6
<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>	1.0	1	1	±0.0

Predatory species showed characteristically low MaxN values (<2), which could be linked with solitary hunting behavior. The modest MaxN of Mysida (1.3) likely reflects high predation pressure limiting group formation near the bait station, as well as the model's limited ability to detect this class (precision = 59%), which may have underestimated their true abundance.

4.3 Competition and Temporal Dynamics

While *S. entomon* and Gobiidae numerically and spatially dominate the community, temporal analysis revealed their dominance is not necessarily fixed but can alternate dynamically between deployments, which could suggest competitive interactions rather than stable hierarchies.

In Deployment 3 (Fig. 5A), Gobiidae dominated, occurring alone in 52,231 frames ($\approx 65\%$), while *S. entomon* appeared alone in 20,409 frames ($\approx 25\%$). *Z. viviparus* appeared mostly alone (455 frames total), with only $\sim 13\%$ of its detections overlapping with other species.

In deployment 4 (Fig. 5B), this pattern reversed, with *S. entomon* and Gobiidae appearing at a similar but reversed ratio. *S. entomon* occurred alone in 94,751 frames ($\approx 69\%$), while Gobiidae occurred alone in 25,324 frames ($\approx 18\%$).

Notably, co-occurrence between these dominant taxa remained consistently low (6-7% of frames), indicating limited temporal overlap and potential active avoidance or competitive exclusion. Predatory species (*P. fluviatilis*, *Z. viviparus*) and other taxa showed minimal overlap (<1% co-occurrence), suggesting distinct ecological niches or temporal partitioning. These dominance inversions might reflect different interacting mechanisms.

When analyzing the entire 18-hour 43-minute dataset in aggregate (Fig. 6), co-occurrence data showed that *S. entomon* and Gobiidae were strongly linked, detected together in the same frame for 399.9 minutes (6.7 hours), the most common occurrence in the entire dataset. This contrasts sharply with their individual appearances. Gobiidae were almost never observed alone (5.3 minutes), whereas *S. entomon* was frequently detected by itself (146.9 minutes), meaning that Gobiidae alone time represents just 3.6% of the *S. entomon* alone time, cementing them as the primary scavenger species in the area.

Figure 5: UpSet plots showing frame-level species co-occurrence patterns for BRUV Deployments 3 (A) and 4 (B), generated from automated object-detection outputs (at 30 fps, 18,000 frames \approx 10 minutes). Vertical bars indicate the number of frames a specific taxa or combination was observed. The matrix below the bars identifies the corresponding class to the bar: single dots represent individual species; connected dots represent co-occurring classes.

Figure 6: Species co-occurrence patterns from all video footage (total 18 hours 43 minutes). The y-axis shows the cumulative time (in minutes) for each combination, calculated from the number of sampled frames (every 5th frame of 30 fps video). The horizontal matrix identifies the species (single dots) or co-occurring combinations (connected dots), corresponding to each bar. Only combinations present in ≥ 180 frames (or 0.5 minutes) are displayed.

4.4 Behavioral Observations

The BRUV footage revealed distinct behavioral patterns and interactions around the bait station. These qualitative observations, noted through manual review of representative video segments, generate testable hypotheses for future quantitative investigation.

4.4.1 Foraging Strategy

S. entomon consistently clustered densely on and inside the bait container, with high detection rates and 100% ubiquity suggesting a dominant, non-aggressive resource acquisition strategy. Gobiidae demonstrated peripheral, opportunistic foraging. Peak goby activity coincided with periods of lower isopod density (Fig. 5B), suggesting active avoidance of competition or interference. Whether this is an example of temporal niche partitioning, microhabitat preferences, competitive exclusion or an artifact of the way the sampling occurred, this remains to be confirmed through more experimentation. Frequent intraspecific chasing also indicated within-species competition for feeding opportunities.

4.4.2 Predator-Prey Dynamics

P. fluviatilis and *Z. viviparus*, primarily patrolled the periphery without extended residence near the bait. While not quantitatively analyzed in this report, their presence appeared to trigger marked behavioral changes in smaller taxa. In Deployment 2, when *P. fluviatilis* was observed hunting Mysida, Gobiidae detections decreased by 96% and *S. entomon* by 97%, suggesting strong predator avoidance responses.

Notably, *S. entomon* populations recovered within 10 minutes despite continued predator presence, while Gobiidae remained largely absent for the rest of the deployment. This differential response likely reflects species-specific anti-predator strategies. Mobile Gobiidae prioritize escape, while armored *S. entomon* exhibit only brief foraging interruptions. These fine-scale behavioral dynamics represent potential community structuring mechanisms warranting further investigation. The bait may also act as an indirect attractant for these predators by concentrating potential prey.

Mysida displayed high vigilance with brief approaches to bait, followed by rapid retreats, consistent with intermediate trophic position and high predation vulnerability.

4.4.3 Spatial Structuring of the Community

Observed behaviors suggest a spatial gradient around the bait:

1. **Core zone:** Dominated by *S. entomon* aggregations directly on bait
2. **Intermediate zone:** Characterized by Gobiidae activity, particularly during low isopod density, and Mysida
3. **Periphery:** Patrolled by predatory fish

These preliminary behavioral insights demonstrate BRUV systems' capacity to reveal fine-scale ecological interactions invisible to traditional sampling. Further investigation through temporal analysis across deployments, spatial heatmapping of species positions, and comparative studies across reef locations is required.

5. Conclusion

This pilot successfully combined consumer-grade hardware with a robust computer vision model (*RF-DETR*, $mAP@50 = 88.8\%$), reducing video analysis time by over 90% while maintaining species-level accuracy. Its implementation within the SUBSIM infrastructure created a reproducible workflow for rapid and repeated ecological assessments of benthic fauna, confirming the technical feasibility of the approach.

The method captured multiple ecological variables that can be used to quantify reef effects, including species richness, abundance, community composition, niche partitioning, and behavioral features such as predator avoidance. We documented eight taxonomic groups at the test site and successfully automated the detection and tracking of six species. The co-occurrence of primary consumers (*S. entomon*), secondary consumers (*Gobiidae*, *Mysida*), and predators (*P. fluviatilis*, *Z. viviparus*) suggests establishment of a functionally complete community at the reef site. However, understanding the effect of the introduced reef structures on these ecological variables will require a comparative study with reference sites.

Artificial reefs present complex monitoring challenges due to their three-dimensional structures, making it difficult to use methods like trawling, filming with drones, or Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) within them. This pilot demonstrates that non-invasive, AI-boosted BRUV systems are ready for operation in these environments. Individual units can be deployed in the vicinity of reef structures without causing disturbance to capture large amounts of ecological data for documenting ecological change and quantification of biodiversity-positive effects.

The approach's cost-effectiveness and operational simplicity enable the joint deployment of many units at the same time, providing extensive spatial and temporal coverage and thereby offering a highly resolved picture of the status and change in the benthic community. The trained detection model and automated pipeline facilitate rapid site characterization and can be used to optimize positive ecological effects through continuous ecosystem modifications within the OWF. Examples for optimisations include arrangement and composition of the benthic reef modules (boulders, plates, tubes, etc.), positioning of nearby aquacultures, or pillar coatings. These approaches are at the heart of the digital twin applications tested in this pilot.

Future iterations of the BRUV construction and hardware optimizations, such as correcting lens distortion and standardizing deployment duration will further enhance data quality and enable the integration of size-based metrics.

While more deployments, footage, and replicates are needed to strengthen statistical power, these results validate AI-assisted BRUV monitoring as a reliable and scalable addition for long-term monitoring and ecological impact assessments at OWFs.

6. Appendix

Appendix A: Technical Specifications

A.1 Camera System

Model	GoPro Hero9 Black
Resolution	1920 × 1080 pixels (1080p)
Frame rate	30 fps
Lens	Linear (distortion correction enabled)
Video Stabilization	Standard (Boost disabled)
Auto-power off	Never
Wifi/Bluetooth/GPS	Off
Image processing	Default color profile, 50% brightness
Storage	128GB SD card

A.2 Housings

Model	Depth Rating	Material	Controls
ActionPro T-Housing	250 m	Aluminium	External: Power, Mode, Record
Redtron Waterproof Housing	60 m	Plastic/Tempered glass	External: Power, Mode, Record

A.3 Power System

Model	External battery: DigiPower Refuel battery pack for GoPro
Power/Battery	4800 mAh
Capacity	6-8 hours continuous recording

A.4 Lighting

Model	Suptiq Waterproof Diving Light
Power/Battery	84-LED, 2600 mAh lithium battery

Brightness	5000 lux
Operating Time	5–7 hours (at minimum brightness)
Depth Rating	50 m
Mounting	Handlebar mount + GoPro screw attachment

A.5 BRUV Frame and Components

Model	SIRUI Traveler 7A
Material	Aluminium
Dimensions	Min. height 48 cm, Max. height 166.5 cm
Weights	Biltema ankle weights 1.5 kg (dry)
Bait container	3D-printed plastic, 70 x 70 x 30 mm
Black contrast mat	Biltema trunk mat

A.6 Recovery System

Rope	30 m, 4 mm polyester line
Buoy	150 mm, 15 bar capacity

A.7 Cost Breakdown (per BRUV unit)

Component	Cost (SEK)	Cost (EUR)
GoPro Hero9	2500	225
T-Housing	4800	435
Refuel Battery Pack	1400	127
Underwater Light	600	54
Tripod + Frame Materials	1300	118
Rope and Buoy	150	13
Bait Container	80	7
Miscellaneous Hardware	250	22
TOTAL PER UNIT	11000 SEK	1000 EUR

Appendix B: Links to Data and Supporting Material

Object detection models:

- RF-DETR model: Available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17429398>

Notebooks:

- [Train Model](#)
- [Evaluate Model](#)

Datasets:

- Annotated training images: Available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17429398>

Code repositories:

- [Analysis scripts \(updated regularly\)](#)

Platforms used

- [SUBSIM](#) -> Data Portals: [ML training](#) and [Analysis](#)
- [Roboflow](#)
- [Lumi HPC](#)

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